

The Intercultural Dimension of Translation: Liliana Corobca in the Anglophone Literary Space³³

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Abstract: *The present study explores the intercultural dimension of translating Liliana Corobca's works from Romanian into English, carried out by Monica Cure. Corobca's novels address topics such as communist censorship, totalitarian trauma, deportations and migration from Eastern Europe, which require contextual adaptation for Anglophone readers.*

The literary translation functions not only as a linguistic transfer, but also as a cultural mediation, which plays a central role in shaping intercultural understanding. Based on interviews with the author and the translator, and reviews from Anglophone literary space, the article highlights the translator's ability to balance between foreignization and domestication while preserving authorial voice and ensuring the accessibility for English readers.

Ultimately, the analysis demonstrates that Cure's translation functions as a bridge between cultures and it is a pragmatic balance between cultural specificity and target language readability.

Keywords: *literary translation, interculturality, Liliana Corobca, Monica Cure, Anglophone literature.*

Introduction

In the context of globalization, literary translation plays a crucial role in establishing dialogue between cultures. This is the way national literature becomes visible internationally. Furthermore,

³³Studiul s-a realizat în cadrul proiectului EUROTRAD, finanțat de ANCD, înscris în Registrul de stat al proiectelor din sfera științei și inovării cu cifrul 25.80013.0807.48ROMD

for authors writing in different languages, translation into English - the dominant lingua franca of global literary works, represents both a great opportunity and a challenge. Moreover, translation is not only seen as a linguistic transfer but as an intercultural process in which meanings and values are negotiated. Said Faiq emphasizes the same fact by saying that “translation is not an isolated act; it is part of an ongoing process of intercultural transfer” (Faiq, 2004, p. 38).

While translating into English, Venuti discusses *domestication* as dominating British and American translation culture; it involves “an ethnocentric reduction of the foreign text to receiving cultural values” (Venuti, 2008, p. 15). This involves translating in a transparent style in order to minimize the foreignness for readers. Along with domestication goes *foreignization*, another strategic cultural intervention that seeks to “send the reader abroad” by making the receiving culture aware of the linguistic and cultural differences inherent in the foreign text (Venuti, 2008, pp. 15–16). By successfully combining both strategies, the translated text resists full integration into dominant Anglophone literary space and stylistics, preserving the foreign narrative rhythm and reinforcing the author’s cultural voice.

1. Liliana Corobca in the anglophone literary space

The last couple of years, there has been an increased interest in Romanian-English translation, like Sean Cotter, Gabi Reigh, Jozefina Komporaly, James Christian Brown etc. Monica Cure is also on the list of successful translators who introduced the works of Liliana Corobca, a Romanian novelist born in the Republic of Moldova, to the Anglophone literary space.

A Censor’s Notebook, a “profound and playful novel” (Zink, 2025) signed by Liliana Corobca, is a fascinating narrative of life in communist Romania, and “a thought-provoking meditation on the nature of literature and censorship” (Carturești). The novel opens “a window onto the secretive world of censorship during that era in Romania” (Broaddus, 2022), or as Seven Stories mentioned: “a window into the intimate workings of censorship under communism, steeped in mystery and secrets and lies, confirming the power of literature to capture personal and political truths” (Seven Stories, 2025). The novel offers much more than a simple story from the past, it is a reminder of constant surveillance and lack of privacy that we all face nowadays. Moreover, Liliana Corobca highlights that “our behaviour, wishes and hopes, and even intentions are monitored, captured and processed, albeit perhaps less by intelligence services and more by tech-powered private entities” and, therefore, the indispensable value of any little bit of privacy resonates strongly in today’s reality (Seven Stories, 2025).

After translating Corobca’s 2017 novel *The Censor’s Notebook*, which won the 2023 Oxford-Weidenfeld Translation Prize, Cure continued with the translation of *Kinderland*, Corobca’s lyrical and heartbreaking 2013 story of childhood abandonment in her native Moldova. *Kinderland* is concerned with the problem of contemporary migration, viewed from a new angle: that of children left at home, with parents working abroad. At the age of twelve, Cristina, the main character of the book, is forced to become the “mother” of the two younger brothers. Through the eyes of the girl, we discover the universe of a contemporary Moldovan/Romanian village, populated mostly by children and old people. Although the book refers to a phenomenon specific to the ex-Soviet space, even nowadays this issue is part of the society.

The same award-winning translator, Monica Cure, worked with the third novel *Too Great a Sky* by Liliana Corobca, “the story of the deportation of Romanians from Bukovina, an exercise in historical memory which demonstrates how to maintain humanity in impossible conditions” (Good Reads). *Too Great a Sky* is a chronicle of a life lived during “a time of great political and national change, a story of an existence defined and curtailed by lines drawn on a map” (The Seven Stories).

Overall, Liliana Corobca’s literary works, deeply embedded in cultural, historical and social frameworks of Eastern Europe, require contextual adaptation for Anglophone readers. On the one hand, the literary works give a historical background of events, inform and educate readers about the social issues of Eastern Europe, and, on the other hand, offer “a lesson for our increasingly complex information age” (Financial Time).

2. Monica Cure as a cultural mediator

The main topics that Corobca highlights in her novels vary from communist censorship, trauma, totalitarianism, deportations, to the problem of contemporary migration. Corobca's texts are full of symbolism, emotional insight and cultural meaning, and thus call for translation and interpretation skills not only in the target language, but also in the target culture. There could not have been a better translator than Monica Cure, who grew up in a Romanian-American community in the US. Her family came from Romania when she was two years old as refugees from the totalitarian communist regime. She adds that translating *The Censor's Notebook* novel gave her a deeper appreciation for the importance of protecting freedom of expression and that "it is healthy to be able to talk about censorship, which is basically the illegitimate silencing of voices" (Publishers Weekly). Scridon Andreea Iulia adds that by being bicultural, "translation was a way of Cure's life" and "the interest in life under the Romanian communist regime helped her understand the novels as whole on a deeper level" (Scridon, 2022).

Monica Cure's role extends beyond linguistic transfer; she acts as an interpreter of cultural meaning. Her translations prove a consistent effort to preserve Corobca's voice while making the texts resonant for Anglophone readers. She confesses that "when she thinks about what she'd like to translate, she thinks of the English language reader, first and foremost. She wants to give them something in which they can both see themselves and their concerns mirrored, something surprisingly familiar because it comes from another culture, as well as be stretched beyond the limits of their knowledge and way of thinking" (The London Magazine). Moreover, Monica Cure "gives to the English language reader something important, something they should know about and experience but have no other way of doing so" (Scridon, 2022). This is due to the fact that "most people in Western Europe and the U.S. have limited knowledge, interest and stereotyped notions about countries that are considered less well-off economically" (Cure, 2022, The London Magazine).

Cure thinks that "the beauty of the literature of places different from our own can create interest in those places when it's available in excellent translations". When dealing with intercultural dimension, Monica Cure admits that it became challenging to "translate looking up all the different cultures and references, which abound in the *Too Great a Sky* novel". While describing nature, tradition, and language of the Kazakh people, there were plenty of cases that needed to be double-checked for historical proof, words in Kazakh which weren't identifiable in the actual language, as Romanian language in Moldova was written with the Cyrillic alphabet and not with Latin (Asymptote Journal).

Furthermore, Cure highlights the challenges of translating culturally marked elements, metaphors grounded in landscapes, for example: "two skies" represent geopolitical borders and divided historical memory. She also acknowledges that some of the translation decisions were to omit the diacritical signs in Romanian names in an attempt to smooth things out for English readers. Another example of translator's choice is the term "well-rounded" instead of the very awkward "multilateral development", which is a word-for-word translation from Romanian "multilateral dezvoltat". This way, Cure adapts the text for the Anglophone world.

Another challenge in translating *Too Great a Sky*, was to deal with the orthodox aspects of the word "troiță", which is a large wooden or stone cross set up at crossroads or to mark an event. In the novel, *Troiță de Sus* is also the (fictional) name of the village in Moldova where Ana settles, and *de sus* can be translated either simply as "upper" in geographic usage or as "from above" in a metaphorical sense. But finally, the part three entitled "Troiță de Sus" in Romanian, kept the most important meaning "roadside crosses" in English, especially since Ana had just shared the memory of the invisible crosses she saw along the train tracks (Cure, *Seven Stories*).

All in all, through a balanced foreignization of rituals or sensory details, Monica Cure's translation is inviting the Anglophone readers into a culturally worldview of source culture. The cultural image of crossroads, for instance, and ritualistic belief goes without explanatory paraphrase and it is not substituted with a culturally equivalent superstition familiar to Anglophone

readers. On the other hand, Cure's choice of domestication of some stylistic devices in translation is also present, for example: "frica îi stătea în gât" is translated into English as "fear gripped her", a more familiar expression. Domestication, in this case, is done to preserve the emotional impact and to ensure easy comprehension.

3. The intercultural dimension of translation

Due to Corobca's extensive research on communist censorship, literary censorship during communist Romania, deportations, migration, her literary works place the national phenomenon in a larger context and reveal its depth. Financial Times highlights the fact that "Corobca's novel should not be categorized as Eastern European interest or communist history, but as an object lesson for our increasingly complex information age" (Financial Times).

Magda Carneci adds that "Liliana Corobca's books have vividly reconstituted the recent histories of countries such as Romania and Moldova before and after the fall of the Berlin Wall in 1989. Her novel *The Censor's Notebook* offers a complete fresco of what censorship meant during the terror, fear, and social control of Ceausescu's totalitarian regime in Romania in the 1970s. Its main character, censor Filoftea Moldovean, is a unique voice in Romanian literature. Through her, the Western reader is able to (re)live the complex thoughts and feelings related to institutional censorship and self-censorship not only in Eastern Europe but in any country" (Carneci, 2022).

Anglophone readers get the historical aspects of the country throughout the novel *Too Great a Sky*, in which "a part of historical Moldova is now in Romania, another part of Bucovina is in Ukraine, and the part called Bessarabia is now in Moldova". The author chooses to highlight different epochs and territories through "folk stories and tales" to introduce the historical background to the reader. The main character experiences a childhood in Bucovina, then in Kazakhstan, after that she works in Siberia, and finally she returns to Soviet Moldova, which becomes post-Soviet Republic of Moldova. There is also a difference in translation of some key words that appear in the novel. In English, the word "exile," is an act of being forced to leave one's country, whereas in Romanian there are plenty forms of *deportation*. The translator adds that the word "exile" and "deportation" are different things (Asymptote Journal) and are perceived differently by the Anglophone readers.

Not only historical aspects are present in Corobca's novels, as Maria Rybakova states, but also intercultural reconstruction of life experiences. If it weren't for Monica Cure and Seven Stories Press, people would never experience the belief in "places of trouble" and in the "magical powers of eggs left at midnight on crossroads"; "the peculiar rituals of village children kissing each other on the butt in an abandoned outhouse to profess undying love; the stench of dung, the noise of chickens, the taste of plums; and the myriad games the abandoned children continually invent to survive the waiting and the separation" (Rybakova, 2024). By rich cultural transfer of beliefs, rituals, sounds etc., translation conveys life experiences which leads to intercultural balance. In such a way, the Anglophone readers access a culturally specific world without erasing its alterity. Consequently, translation emerges as a balanced act between fidelity to source-culture and the demand of accessibility in the target language.

Costica Bradatan adds that Monica Cure "shuttles with ease and grace between strikingly different stylistic and lexical registers, from officials and propaganda to the more intimate and even lyrical. Out of this varied material a lucid narrative slowly emerges" (Bradatan, 2022).

Conclusion

The examination of Liliana Corobca's works in English translation reveals the crucial importance of literary translation as an intercultural phenomenon, rather than a linguistic one. Monica Cure's translations of Corobca's works represent a deliberate process of balancing source culture and loyalty and target culture accessibility through a strategic combination of foreignization and domestication. Cultural signs associated with communist censorship, collective trauma, everyday life, and historical memory are not suppressed but rather skillfully mediated in order to enable the target culture audience to access foreign realities without losing their cultural distinctiveness.

The study proves that the translated works of Corobca are a part of the intercultural dialogue process, as they bring Eastern European experiences into the Anglophone literary space, which is dominated by a lack of representation of Eastern European narratives.

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